

Research Symposium: Gender & Democratic Backsliding

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Democratic backsliding continues to be a *hot* topic in political science, especially in light of the global rise in authoritarian tendencies and democratic erosions. At the most basic level, democratic backsliding refers to incremental changes that undermines the foundations of democracy. David Waldner and Ellen Lust (2018) rightly distinguish between democratic backsliding within democratic regimes and autocratic ones. In democratic regimes, democratic backsliding marks “a decline in the quality of democracy;” in autocratic regimes, “it is a decline in democratic qualities of governance” (Waldner and Lust 2018, 95).

In the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, where regimes either radically or gradually weaken such democratic elements, scholars have extensively analyzed how autocracies suppress democratic reforms, mitigate their impacts, or entirely dismantle democratic advancements. However, gender remains a critical yet underexplored lens in the scholarship. A gender lens helps us better identify, measure, and assess the process of democratic backsliding. To help us understand democratic backsliding from a gender lens, we turned to our colleagues who study gender politics in the MENA region. We asked them to answer the following question: “How does examining democratic backsliding through a gender lens contribute to our understanding of its dynamics?”

Besides the academic impetus for dedicating a symposium to the topic, we also had personal impetus. As we, the outgoing editors of the newsletter, gathered to brainstorm ideas

for our final issue and stared at each other’s Zoom boxes, it hit us: we have an editorial team with two scholars of gender politics, yet we have not produced a symposium on the topic. It does not reflect well on our *legacy*.

Do the academic and personal motivations for dedicating this symposium suggest that I am, perhaps ironically, engaging in *signaling*? I hope I am not. I hope I am not influenced by or staying true to *Mama Suzanne*, the former first lady of Egypt who, like her counterparts in many MENA countries, championed gender equality policies in service of the regime’s signaling agenda. This passing thought, however, further deepened my commitment to approaching the topic with humility, a serious acknowledgment of its complexity, and a renewed dedication to carefully unpack its intertwined dynamics. Collectively and individually, our contributors did just that.

Collectively, the contributions unpack the relationship between gender politics and democratic backsliding. They (a) explore how both the repression and superficial expansion of women’s rights signal the erosion of democratic institutions, and (b) demonstrate how studying both has broader implications for understanding democratic erosion and authoritarian entrenchment in the MENA region.

The contributions emphasize that the repression of women’s rights—and the rollback of gender reforms—serves as an early indicator of democratic backsliding, a reflection of the deeper structural issues within governance

and civil liberties, and a measure of the trajectory of authoritarian entrenchment.

Aili Mari Tripp shows how the decline in women's parliamentary representation in Algeria signifies a broader democratic stagnation within the political system. Yuree Noh further explores this theme across different cases in the MENA region, she demonstrates how authoritarian incumbents in Turkey, Algeria, and Iraq systematically undermine women's rights to gain conservative support while simultaneously eroding democratic norms and institutions. In Jordan, Marwa Shalaby illustrates that election manipulation signals the onset of both democratic and gender backsliding. Although gender quota mechanisms can alleviate some negative outcomes, the instability and manipulation of the electoral landscape, she holds, severely restrict women's access to power. This pattern of erosion extends to the overall state apparatus, as Rita Stephan demonstrates: the hollowing of state institutions leads to a corresponding decline in women's rights and other civic liberties. In Iran, Mona Tajali further elaborates on the connection between gender oppression and the broader health of governance by showing how intensified policing of women's bodies and restrictions on feminist activism signify deeper authoritarian entrenchment. The regime's violent crackdowns on movements like "Woman, Life, Freedom" illustrate how authoritarian regimes leverage gender repression as a tool to consolidate their power.

While a decline in women's rights clearly signals democratic backsliding, a less intuitive but equally telling indicator is when the expansion of women's rights is used by regimes to erode democratic institutions and consolidate autocratic rule. In such cases, state-led gender reforms may thus mark the onset

of a silent, obscured process of "autocratic genderwashing" (Bjarnegård and Zetterberg 2022), democratic containment, and/or democratic erosion. Regimes in the MENA region often manipulate women's rights and gender reforms to legitimize anti-democratic, right-wing movements, suppress political opposition, distract from human rights violations, and justify punitive governance.

For example, Madawi Al-Rasheed demonstrates in her contribution on Saudi Arabia that women's rights are not advanced for genuine equality or political reform in the kingdom but are manipulated as tools of statecraft to divide opposition and reinforce the monarchy's control. Crown Prince Mohamed Bin Salman has instrumentalized gender reforms to create a facade of progress through expanding women's rights while intensifying crackdowns on independent feminist voices. In Egypt, al-Sisi's selective reforms, such as addressing sexual-based violence while avoiding changes to personal status laws, illustrate how gender reforms are used to reinforce his regime's carceral logic and security narrative. Personal status laws remain unchanged because they uphold traditional power structures that the regime relies on for support. Meanwhile, the regime's approach to sexual-based violence reforms aligns with increased surveillance, policing, and punitive measures rather than genuine social or political reforms.

Beyond state-led manipulation, Hind Ahmed Zaki highlights how feminists themselves can sometimes become entangled in this process. In Tunisia, she demonstrates that feminist legal campaigns, while achieving notable gains for women's rights, unintentionally reconfigured state sovereignty. By appealing to the state's punitive and interventionist policies during moments of political upheaval, femi-

nist movements contributed to consolidating state authority. It allowed the regime to maintain control and provide impunity to police forces in the aftermath of Tunisia's democratic transition.

So, given that regimes manipulate women's rights, is it acceptable for political actors to ignore women's issues while pushing for or protecting democratic reforms, norms, and institutions? Absolutely not—no, please no. I get triggering flashbacks remembering when audiences selectively latch onto specific aspects of what is otherwise a larger, nuanced argument about gender politics, using them to support the fallacy of 'let's put women's rights on the back burner.' While a decline in women's rights is a clear indicator of democratic backsliding, the manipulative expansion of these rights by authoritarian regimes represents a nuanced indicator of deteriorating democratic institutions. Analyzing the complex relationship between gender and democratic erosion enables us to explain, measure, and infer broader trends and patterns of democratic decline. Such an analysis sharpens our methodological tools, refines our analytical lens, and qualifies our empirical findings in the following meaningful ways.

First, examining democratic backsliding through a gender lens demonstrates the ways in which democratic backsliding is intertwined with various structural forces, such as class dynamics, social inequalities, and international militarism. In her introductory piece for the symposium, Valentine M. Moghadam emphasizes the importance of integrating a gender lens with class analysis to trace how these structural forces collectively drive democratic backsliding. Together they contribute to an environment where hegemonic masculinity and pervasive chauvinism not only

prevail in the socio-political sphere but also serve as fundamental factors undermining democratic principles in domestic and international politics.

Second, in measuring democratic backsliding, Gamze Çavdar proposes a reconceptualization of democracy that places gender equality at its core. She advocates for the use of comparative and/or small-N studies to examine multiple indicators of democratic backsliding, including socio-economic changes, the repression of women's organizations, and shifts in gender discourses. This approach offers several methodological advantages: it effectively measures variations in the degrees of democratic backsliding both within and across countries, illuminates not only patterns but also the mechanisms underlying democratic backsliding, and centers the human experiences and stories of those resisting such decline.

Third, a gender lens helps us qualify our findings and analyses. It highlights variations in the strategies used by autocratic regimes to stifle democratic reforms, mitigate their effects, or entirely dismantle democratic advancements. The authors in this symposium identify techniques ranging from electoral manipulation (see Marwa Shalaby; Alexandra Domike Blackman in this symposium) and political repression (see Madawi al-Rasheed; Mona Tajali; Summer Forester; Rita Stephan in this symposium) to state cooptation (see Yuree Noh; Hind Ahmed Zaki in this symposium) and deliberate openings and closures (see Aili Mari Tripp; Carolyn Barnett in this symposium) in response to domestic and international political currents. Applying a gender lens to democratic backsliding also uncovers how different institutions and issues are targeted differently by authoritarian regimes. In her analysis of Jordan, Summer

Forester highlights that family laws and independent feminist spaces—but not the state-sponsored Jordanian National Commission of Women (JNCW)—were particularly vulnerable to democratic erosion given their relationship with antidemocratic developments.

Finally, studying democratic backsliding through a gender lens helps us qualify and evaluate democratic reforms on the ground. Rather than uncritically approaching gender advancements as indicators of democratic reforms, researchers should (a) investigate how these reforms are negotiated and (b) trace their broader impacts. A critical analysis of gender reforms and their outcomes allows researchers to assess whether these changes are genuine or superficial, and consequently identify the broader democratic—or autocratic—impulses at play. If reforms are strictly top-down and divorced from civil society, they may not lead to meaningful democratic shifts, and they may signal a risk of democratic backsliding. For example, Carolyn Barnett argues that advances in women's rights in Morocco are used by the regime to “backslide forward.” She contends that the top-down approach adopted by the regime in reforming the Mudawana may paradoxically reinforce the misconception that popular support for gender equality is weak, positions the regime as the “savior” of women, and undermines officials' willingness to enforce laws—as it implies that the advancements clash with societal norms. Relatedly, if reforms do not lead to broader democratic shifts, they may also signal democratic backsliding. For example, Alexandra Domike Blackman demonstrates that, in Tunisia, while women may achieve prominent roles in anti-democratic movements, their overall political representation often declines. Rather than narrowly focusing on a single aspect of women's political repre-

sentation, tracing their broader impacts offers a more accurate assessment of the health of democratic institutions.

We believe this symposium raises and answers important questions for studying gender politics and democratic backsliding. The short and accessible format of the entries is meant to provide researchers with a concise set of meaningful theoretical frameworks, robust methodological tools, and solid empirical data.

And just like that, as the outgoing co-editor of the APSA MENA newsletter, I feel we have done justice to our legacy! ♦

References

- Bjarnegård, Elin, and Pär Zetterberg. 2022. “How Autocrats Weaponize Women's Rights.” *Journal of Democracy* 33(2): 60–75.
- Waldner, David, and Ellen Lust. 2018. “Unwelcome Change: Coming to Terms with Democratic Backsliding.” *Annual Review of Political Science* 21(Volume 21, 2018): 93–113.